

Indigenous Traditional Knowledge of Forest Resource Management Among Aka Tribes of Arunachal Pradesh

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In rural communities, indigenous traditional knowledge serves as the foundation for local decision-making about agriculture, healthcare, food preparation, education, natural resource management and a wide range of other topics. The preservation of forest resources is a burning issue in worldwide. There are numerous sub-tribes and around 26 major tribes in Arunachal Pradesh. Forest and its resources serve as the main source of economy and livelihood sustenance of tribal communities. Indigenous Traditional knowledge (ITK), developed and practiced by tribals are essential to the preservation of forest resources. An analysis of the sacred groves, ITK and beliefs of the Aka tribes in relation to the preservation of forest resources has been attempted. The indigenous knowledge associated with protection of sacred groves, wildlife, and floras have been discussed with local people of the villages. For primary data, household survey is conducted in 30 villages inhabited by Aka tribe with the help of a pre-designed questionnaire.

Keywords: *Forest conservation, ITK, Rural community, sacred groves*